

THE EFFECT OF SERVICE QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE AND PROMOTION ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AT CV. ABC HARDWARE INDUSTRY MEDAN SUNGGAL

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Abstract

This study aims to determine and analyze the effect of service quality, brand image, and promotion on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal using a quantitative descriptive correlational approach. The sample consisted of 62 respondents selected through simple random sampling using the Slovin formula from customers who made transactions during January–July 2025. Data were collected through a Likert-scale questionnaire and analyzed using multiple linear regression with SPSS, including validity, reliability, classical assumption tests, t-test, F-test, and coefficient of determination. The results show that partially service quality (t-value 2.778; sig 0.007), brand image (t-value 4.405; sig 0.000), and promotion (t-value 2.439; sig 0.018) have a significant effect on customer satisfaction, and simultaneously these three variables also have a significant effect with an F-value of 212.456 and sig 0.000. The Adjusted R Square value of 0.912 indicates that 91.2% of the variation in customer satisfaction can be explained by service quality, brand image, and promotion.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Brand Image, Promotion, Customer Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Service, brand perception, and advertising are the most influential factors in customer satisfaction in any market, especially in industries where customers have high expectations about the quality of products and services offered. CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal is a company engaged in the distribution of materials for PLN and Telkom. To meet increasing competition, this company needs to maintain its service quality, improve its brand image, and at the same time employ appropriate marketing strategies to satisfy its customers and maintain their loyalty. Previous research has highlighted the influence of service, brand perception, and advertising on customer satisfaction, but most are still limited to the retail or e-commerce context. For example, Parahyangan et al. (2022) examined service quality and corporate image in a trucking company and found that corporate image and service quality influence loyalty through customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, Tadulako University (2023) emphasized the importance of digital marketing strategies on customer satisfaction, though the context is still general.

Problem Identification

Based on the background, the identification of problems in this research is as follows:

1. The service provided has not consistently met customer expectations, thus reducing the level of satisfaction.
2. The company's brand image is not yet strong in the minds of customers so it has not fully built trust.
3. Promotional activities are not yet effective and have not been able to attract customer attention optimally.
4. Customers are not yet fully satisfied because the quality of service, brand image, and promotion are not yet optimal.

Formulation of the problem

This study aims to determine and analyze the influence of service quality, brand image, and promotion on customer satisfaction at CV ABC HARDWARE INDUSTRY MEDAN SUNGGAL. The problem formulation written in this study is:

1. Does service quality partially have a significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal?
2. Does brand image partially have a significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal?
3. Does partial promotion have a significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal?
4. Do service quality, brand image and promotion simultaneously have a significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal?

Research purposes

Based on the formulation of the problem, the research objectives are as follows:

1. To determine and analyze the partial influence of service quality on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.
2. To determine and analyze the partial influence of brand image on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.
3. To determine and analyze the partial influence of promotion on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.
4. To determine and analyze the influence of service quality, brand image, and promotion simultaneously on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a customer's emotional response after comparing the service performance received with their expectations. According to Kotler and Keller (2020), satisfaction arises when product or service performance meets or exceeds customer expectations. Similarly, Tjiptono (2021) explains that customer satisfaction is influenced by their perceptions of service quality, perceived value, and overall experience with the company. Recent research also confirms that customer satisfaction is a crucial indicator in maintaining loyalty and long-term relationships with customers (Bachri et al., 2023). Therefore, customer satisfaction can be defined as the result of a comprehensive evaluation of the customer's consumption experience with the service or product received.

Quality of Service

Service quality is a customer's assessment of the reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles of the service. According to Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler (2020), good service quality is service that meets or even exceeds customer expectations through the SERVQUAL dimension. Meanwhile, Lupiyoadi (2021) emphasized that service quality reflects a company's ability to provide services quickly, accurately, and satisfactorily to customers. Recent research also shows that service quality significantly influences customer satisfaction because customers expect a fast, accurate, and professional response from service providers (Putri & Kurniawan, 2022). Therefore, improving service quality is an important strategy for increasing customer satisfaction.

Brand Image

Brand image is a customer's perception of a brand formed through experiences, information, and interactions with the company. Keller (2020) states that brand image is formed from strong, favorable, and unique associations embedded in consumers' minds. Schiffman and Wisenblit (2020) also explain that brand image influences how consumers evaluate a product, make purchasing decisions, and determine customer loyalty. Recent research by Dewi and Pratama (2023) shows that a strong brand image can increase customer trust and positive attitudes toward a company, thereby impacting customer satisfaction. Thus, a positive brand image is a crucial asset for companies in building long-term relationships with customers.

Promotion

Promotion is a company's strategic step to inform, persuade, and remind customers about the products or services offered. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2021), effective promotion can increase customer awareness, build interest, and drive purchasing decisions through a promotional mix such as advertising, sales promotions, personal selling, and digital marketing. Tjiptono (2020) added that persuasive and targeted promotions can provide added value to customers and increase a company's competitiveness. Recent research by Sari and Nugroho (2024) shows that digital promotion through social media is highly effective in reaching customers and influencing their perceptions of the company. This confirms that a well-planned promotional strategy can significantly impact customer satisfaction.

Conceptual Framework

The following is the conceptual framework in this research, as follows:

Figure 1.1 Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

- H1: Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.
- H2: Brand image has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.
- H3: Promotion has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.
- H4: Service quality, brand image, and promotion simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.

METHOD

Types and Approaches

This research uses a quantitative approach with a descriptive correlational approach, which aims to examine the relationship between existing variables. This approach allows researchers to explore the influence of each factor (service quality, brand image, and promotion) on customer satisfaction.

Place and Time of Research

The location of this research is CV ABC Hardware Industry, which has the complete address at Jalan Sunggal No. 150-152, Medan City, North Sumatra, and the time of this research is in the period January-July 2025.

Population and Sample

The population in this study were all customers of CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal, who had made transactions in the period January-July 2025. The research sample was determined using a simple random sampling technique to ensure random and representative selection from the population, namely 165 people.

The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula and a 10% error rate, resulting in a sample size of 62 respondents. The sampling technique used was *simple random sampling*, so that each member of the population had an equal chance of being selected as a respondent in this study.

$$n = \frac{165}{1 + 165(0,1)^2} = \frac{165}{1 + 165(0,01)} = \frac{165}{1 + 1,65} = \frac{165}{2,65} \approx 62,26$$

The research sample consisted of 62 customers, randomly selected from the company's total customer population. This sampling aimed to obtain data representing customers' views on service quality, brand image, promotions, and perceived customer satisfaction.

Identification and Operational Definition of Research

The operational definition of the research variables is as follows:

Variables	Operational Definition	Indicator	Measurement Scale
Service Quality (X1)	Service quality is the level of excellence of a product or service that is expected to meet the level of excellence to meet consumer desires. (Tjiptono, 2021)	1. Physical evidence 2. Reliability 3. Responsiveness 4. Guarantee 5. Empathy (Tjiptono, 2021)	Likert Scale
Brand Image (X2)	Brand image represents the overall perception of a brand and is formed from information and knowledge about that brand (Lupiyoadi, 2021).	1. <i>Brand Trust</i> 2. <i>Brand Recognition</i> 3. <i>Brand Association</i> 4. <i>Perceived Quality</i> (Lupiyoadi, 2021).	Likert Scale
Promotion (X3)	Promotion is any form of communication used to inform, persuade or remind people about products produced by organizations, individuals or households. (Keller, 2020).	1. Advertisement 2. Direct marketing 3. Public relations (Keller, 2020).	Likert Scale
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	Customer satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment in comparing the consumer's impression of the actual or actual level of product and service performance with the expected performance. (Armstrong, 2021)	1. Conformity to expectations 2. Satisfaction with the process 3. Repurchase intention 4. Minimal complaints (Armstrong, 2021)	Likert Scale

Data Analysis Techniques

The data obtained will be analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis techniques to test the effect of service quality, brand image, and promotion on customer satisfaction. This analysis is carried out with the help of statistical software such as SPSS or other statistical applications to ensure the validity and reliability of the data. By using a sample of 62 people, this study can provide a fairly representative picture of the effect of service quality, brand image, and promotion on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.

Classical Assumption Test

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to determine whether a correlation exists between independent variables in a regression model. A good regression model should have no correlation between independent variables. If a correlation does occur, it is considered a multicollinearity problem. This symptom can be detected by measuring the *Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)* using SPSS (Rusiadi et al., 2020). Sujarweni (2021) explains that a multicollinearity test is necessary to determine whether there are similar independent variables in a model. Similarities between independent variables will result in a very strong correlation.

In addition, this test is conducted to avoid habits in the decision-making process regarding the influence of the partial test of each independent variable used on the dependent variable. The provisions for detecting the presence of j The presence or absence of multicollinearity is: • $VIF > 10$ and Tolerance value < 0.1 means there is a multicollinearity problem • $VIF < 10$ and Tolerance value > 0.1 means there is no multicollinearity problem

The tolerance value can be found using the formula: $Tolerance = (1 - R^2)$ Where R^2 = the determination value of the regression. The VIF value can be found using the formula: $VIF = (1/Tolerance)$

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is used to determine whether there is inequality in the variance of residuals from one observation to another. A regression model that meets these requirements is one in which the residuals from one observation to another remain the same, or homoscedasticity (Rusiadi et al., 2020). Heteroscedasticity can be detected using the scatterplot method by plotting the ZPRED value (predicted value) with the SRESID (residual value). A good model is one that does not show a specific pattern on the graph, such as clustering in the middle, narrowing then widening, or conversely widening then narrowing. Statistical tests that can be used are the Glejser test, the Park test, or the White test (Rusiadi et al., 2020).

Hypothesis Testing

T-Test (Partial)

The T-test aims to assess the influence of individual independent variables on the dependent variable. The formula used is:

$$t = \frac{b}{sb}$$

Information:

t = t-count, b = Regression coefficient, sb = Standard error of factor X

Hypothesis testing criteria:

If $sig < 0.05$ or $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$, then the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable, and if $sig > 0.05$ or $t\text{-count} < t\text{-table}$, then the independent variable does not have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

F Test (Simultaneous)

The F-test is conducted to assess whether all independent variables collectively influence the dependent variable. According to Ghozali (2021) in a study by Langitan et al. (2024), the F-test is often misunderstood as a partial test.

Decision making criteria:

If $Sig F < 0.05$, then the regression model is significant and can be used (H_0 is rejected), and if $Sig F \geq 0.05$, then the regression model is not significant and cannot be used (H_0 is accepted).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research result

Validity Test

The reliability of the scales derived from the variables was checked using a validity test.

- If $r_{count} > r_{table}$ then it is said to be valid.
- If $r_{count} < r_{table}$ then it is said to be valid.

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variables	Statement	r-count	r table Df = N - 2	Information
Quality of Service	1	0.554	0.25	Valid
	2	0.804	0.25	Valid
	3	0.59	0.25	Valid
	4	0.397	0.25	Valid
	5	0.646	0.25	Valid
	6	0.804	0.25	Valid
	7	0.42	0.25	Valid
	8	0.397	0.25	Valid

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Variables	Statement	r-count	r table Df = N - 2	Information
	9	0.554	0.25	Valid
	10	0.804	0.25	Valid
Brand Image	1	0.53	0.25	Valid
	2	0.804	0.25	Valid
	3	0.437	0.25	Valid
	4	0.804	0.25	Valid
	5	0.437	0.25	Valid
	6	0.684	0.25	Valid
	7	0.577	0.25	Valid
	8	0.804	0.25	Valid
	9	0.577	0.25	Valid
	10	0.804	0.25	Valid
Promotion	1	0.71	0.25	Valid
	2	0.795	0.25	Valid
	3	0.795	0.25	Valid
	4	0.46	0.25	Valid
	5	0.445	0.25	Valid
	6	0.715	0.25	Valid
	7	0.71	0.25	Valid
	8	0.795	0.25	Valid
	9	0.71	0.25	Valid
	10	0.656	0.25	Valid
Customer satisfaction	1	0.721	0.25	Valid
	2	0.793	0.25	Valid
	3	0.793	0.25	Valid
	4	0.569	0.25	Valid
	5	0.554	0.25	Valid
	6	0.723	0.25	Valid
	7	0.721	0.25	Valid
	8	0.793	0.25	Valid
	9	0.721	0.25	Valid
	10	0.667	0.25	Valid

Source: Processed by Researchers (2025)

Based on table .1, it can be explained that the calculated r-value for each statement in the variables of service quality, brand image, promotion, and customer satisfaction is greater than the r-table = 0.25. It can be concluded that each statement of service quality, brand image, promotion, and customer satisfaction is valid.

Reliability Test Reliability is a method for evaluating the reliability of a questionnaire, reflecting the stability or consistency of the variables or constructs being measured. A questionnaire is considered reliable if an individual's responses to the questions remain consistent over time. As a general guideline, an instrument is considered reliable if its Cronbach's alpha value exceeds the threshold of 0.60. Conversely, if the Cronbach's alpha value is less than 0.60, the instrument is considered unreliable or lacking consistency.

Table .2 2Service Quality Reliability Test

No	Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Alpha Standard	Information
1	Quality of Service	0.792	0.6	Reliable
2	Brand Image	0.844	0.6	Reliable
3	Promotion	0.866	0.6	Reliable
4	Customer satisfaction	0.855	0.6	Reliable

Source: Processed by Researchers (2025)

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The multiple linear regression analysis test method is used to see how much influence the quality of service, brand image and promotion of CV ABC Hardware Industry have. The provisions of the multiple linear regression analysis equation can be formulated as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

The results of the multiple linear regression analysis test can be seen in the following table:

Table 3 Multiple Linear Regression Test Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8,209	1,830		4,485	.000
	Quality of Service	.124	.045	.123	2,778	.007
	Brand Image	.577	.131	.662	4,405	.000
	Promotion	.350	.144	.360	2,439	.018

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source : Processed by researchers (202 5)

$$\text{Customer Satisfaction} = 8.209 + 0.124 \text{ service quality} + 0.577 \text{ brand image} + 0.350 \text{ promotion} + e$$

The explanation of the multiple linear regression analysis above is:

1. The constant of 8.209 means that if service quality (X1), brand image (X2), and promotion (X3) have a value of 0, then customer satisfaction will increase by 8.209 units .
2. Service quality coefficient (b1) = 0.124 means that if the service quality increases by 1 unit, then the service quality will increase by 0.124 units .
3. Brand image coefficient (b2) = 0.577 means that if the brand image increases by 1 unit, the brand image will increase by 0.577 units .
4. Promotion coefficient (b3) = 0.350 means that if the promotion increases by 1 unit, the promotion will increase by 0.350 units .

Normality Test

The normality test in this research is used to determine and analyze whether the regression model of the dependent and independent variables is normally distributed or not. The methods used to test the normality of the data in this study are histogram graphs, normal P-plot graphs, and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

Figure 1. Normality Test of Histogram Graph

Source : Processed by researchers (202 5)

Based on Figure 3.1. above, it can be seen that the line on the histogram graph shows that the residuals have a normal distribution pattern, marked by a symmetrical normal curve line to the left and right that encompasses the data.

The results of the P-Plot normal graph test can be described as follows:

Figure .2 2P Plot Normality Test

Source : Processed by researchers (202 5)

Based on Figure 3.2. The Normal P-Plot graph shows that the data is spread around the diagonal line so it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

**Table 4. One-Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test**

		Unstandardize d Residual
N		62
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Standard Deviation	1.30418958
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.095
	Positive	.095
	Negative	-.066
Test Statistics		.095
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Source: Processed by Researchers (2025)

Based on table 4. above, the asymp. Sig value is $0.200 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

The results of the multicollinearity test can be seen in the table below:

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

Model		Coefficients ^a				Collinearity Statistics		
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	8,209	1,830		4,485	.000		
	Quality of Service	.124	.045	.123	2,778	.007	.735	1,360
	Brand Image	.577	.131	.662	4,405	.000	.064	5,699
	Promotion	.350	.144	.360	2,439	.018	.066	5,139

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source : Processed by researchers (2025)

Based on table 5. above, it shows that the tolerance value of the service quality variable has a value of $0.735 > 0.01$ and the VIF value of the independent variable has a value of $1.360 < 10$. The tolerance value of the brand image variable has a value of $0.064 > 0.01$ and the VIF value of the independent variable has a value of $5.699 < 10$. The tolerance value of the promotion variable has a value of $0.066 > 0.01$ and the VIF value of the independent variable has a value of $5.139 < 10$, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is used to determine whether there is inequality in the variance of residual variables from one observation to another. The results of the heteroscedasticity test using the scatterplot test can be seen in the following table:

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Source : Processed by researchers (202 5)

In Figure 3, the scatterplot shows that the data points are spread out, the points are spread out above and below zero on the y-axis, so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in this study.

Coefficient of Determination

The results of the coefficient of determination test can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.957 ^a	.917	.912	1.33749

a. Predictors: (Constant), Promotion, Service Quality, Brand Image

Source : Processed by researchers (202 5)

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Based on table 6, it shows that the Adjusted R Square is 0.912, then $0.912 \times 100\%$ which means that service quality, brand image, and promotion can explain customer satisfaction by 91%, then the remaining 9% is explained by other variables outside this study such as: discounts, payment time, product quality and other variables.

T-Test (Partial)

The results of the partial hypothesis test (t-test) can be seen in the following table:

Table 7. T-Test (Partial) Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8,209	1,830		4,485	.000
	Quality of Service	.124	.045	.123	2,778	.007
	Brand Image	.577	.131	.662	4,405	.000
	Promotion	.350	.144	.360	2,439	.018

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source : Processed by researchers (202 5)

The ttable value for a significance of 0.05 is obtained through the formula

$$df = n - k$$

$$df = 62 - 4 = 58$$

so that the ttable value is obtained = 1.672

Based on the results of the t-test in table 7. above, it can be explained as follows:

1. In the service quality variable (X1), it can be seen that the t-count value (2.778) > t-table (1.672) with a significance of $0.007 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is an influence of service quality on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal, so H1 is accepted.
2. In the brand image variable (X2), it can be seen that the calculated t value (4.405) > t table (1.672) with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is an influence of brand image on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal, so that H2 is accepted.
3. In the promotion variable (X3), it can be seen that the calculated t value (2.439) > t table (1.672) with a significance of $0.018 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is an influence of promotion on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal, so H3 is accepted.

F Test (Simultaneous)

The results of the simultaneous hypothesis test (f-test) can be seen in the following table:

Table 8. F Test (Simultaneous)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1140.180	3	380,060	212,456	.000 ^b
	Residual	103,756	58	1,789		
	Total	1243,935	61			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Promotion, Service Quality, Brand Image

Source : Processed by researchers (202 5)

To see the Ftable value, you can use the following formula:

$$df = nk = 62 - 4 = 58$$

So that the Ftable value can be obtained as 2.531

Based on Table 8, it shows that the F count value (212.456) > F table (2.531) with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that H4 is accepted or there is an influence of service quality, brand

image, and promotion on customer satisfaction at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal, so H4 is accepted.

Discussion

The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the results of the partial test (t-test), the calculated t-value was $2.778 > t\text{-table } 1.672$ with a significance level of $0.007 < 0.05$, so that service quality (X1) has a significant effect on customer satisfaction (Y). This shows that the better the quality of service provided by CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal, the more customer satisfaction will increase. The results of this study align with Tjiptono's (2011) statement that service quality is a consumer's assessment of the superiority of the service received compared to their expectations. When a company is able to meet these requirements of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, customer satisfaction levels will increase. This research also aligns with research by Parahyangan et al. (2022), which states that service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction in the B2B industry. Furthermore, research by Bachri et al. (2023) explains that service quality is a crucial factor influencing customer satisfaction levels because it can build positive perceptions and enhance customer satisfaction during transactions.

The Influence of Brand Image on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the partial test results, the t-value was $4.405 > 1.672$ with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating that brand image (X2) has a significant influence on customer satisfaction (Y). This means that the better the brand image a company has, the higher the level of trust, positive perception, and customer loyalty will be. These results support Buchari's (2004) theory that brand image is a form of consumer perception and belief in a brand based on experiences and information stored in the consumer's memory. When a brand has a strong reputation, customers will feel more confident and satisfied when making purchases. The findings of this study support the research of Parahyangan et al. (2022), which found that corporate image significantly influences customer satisfaction and loyalty. Furthermore, these results align with research by Bachri et al. (2023), which found that brand perception influences consumer satisfaction levels and purchasing decisions.

The Effect of Promotion on Customer Satisfaction

The partial test results show a t-value of $2.439 > 1.672$ with a significance of $0.018 < 0.05$, thus concluding that promotion (X3) has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. This means that the more appropriate the promotional media used, the better the information received by consumers, thereby increasing trust and satisfaction. According to Simamora's theory (2000), promotion is an important communication tool that companies can use to influence, inform, and persuade customers to learn about and use the products or services they offer. Effective promotion helps customers gain a clear understanding of the product's benefits, leading to post-purchase satisfaction. The results of this study also support the study by Tadulako University (2023) which explains that marketing strategies, especially digital marketing, have a significant influence on customer satisfaction because they provide information that is fast and easy for consumers to accept.

The Influence of Service Quality, Brand Image, and Promotion on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the results of the simultaneous test (F-test), the F-count value obtained was $212.456 > 2.531$ with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, so that service quality (X1), brand image (X2), and promotion (X3) together had a significant effect on customer satisfaction (Y). Based on the coefficient of determination, the Adjusted R-Square value was obtained at 0.912, which means that the variables of service quality, brand image, and promotion are able to explain 91% of the customer satisfaction variable, while 9% is influenced by other factors such as price, product quality, stock availability, delivery speed, and sales communication. These results support the marketing theory that customer satisfaction is influenced by a combination of good service, strong branding, and appropriate promotional communications. Empirically, these findings are consistent with research by Parahyangan et al. (2022) and Bachri et al. (2023), which explains that marketing variables are interrelated in influencing customer satisfaction levels.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The t-test results show that the service quality variable has a significant effect on customer satisfaction with a calculated t value (2.778) > t table (1.672) and a significance of 0.007 < 0.05. This means that the better the quality of service provided by CV ABC Hardware Industry, the higher the level of customer satisfaction. The regression coefficient value of 0.124 indicates that a small increase in service quality can significantly increase customer satisfaction.
2. The analysis results show that brand image has the most dominant influence on customer satisfaction with a calculated t value (4.405) > t table (1.672) and a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. The regression coefficient of 0.577 indicates that positive perceptions of the CV ABC Hardware Industry brand contribute strongly to increasing customer satisfaction. This means that customers who assess the company's brand as reliable, professional, and trustworthy will tend to be more satisfied with the products and services.
4. The promotion variable also significantly influences customer satisfaction, with a calculated t value (2.439) > t table (1.672) and a significance level of 0.018 < 0.05. The regression coefficient value of 0.350 indicates that the more effective the company's promotions, the higher the level of customer satisfaction. This proves that promotional activities can attract attention and increase customers' positive perceptions of the company.
5. The customer satisfaction variable is simultaneously influenced by service quality, brand image, and promotion, with the F test results showing a calculated F value (212.456) > F table (2.531) and a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. The Adjusted R² value of 0.912 indicates that 91.2% of the variation in customer satisfaction can be explained by the three independent variables. This shows that the research model is very strong and relevant to the conditions at CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal.

Suggestion

Based on the conclusions above, the following suggestions can be given:

1. For CV ABC Hardware Industry Medan Sunggal
Improving the quality of service, especially in the aspects of responsiveness and empathy, such as accelerating responses to customer requests, increasing the timeliness of service, and providing personal attention to customers to create strong long-term relationships.
2. For the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University
It is hoped that the Faculty of Economics can add research references in the business scope because similar research is still more dominant in the retail and e-commerce sectors.
3. For Further Researchers
It is recommended to add other variables such as product quality, price, customer trust, customer experience, digital marketing, or after-sales service, so as to provide broader and more in-depth study results.

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